

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TECHNOLOGY OF PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING AS A MEANS OF FORMING EDUCATIONAL AND COGNITIVE COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS

Kismetova G.,

*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University*

Deina L.

*Master's student of the philological faculty,
Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University*

Abstract

The article discusses the actual aspects of the application of problem-based learning technology in the formation of students' competencies. The essence of the concept of «problem-based learning» is indicated, the main characteristics are highlighted. The stages of working with the technology of problem-based learning are analyzed, appropriate methods that contribute to the formation of competencies are considered. The types of problematic situations that activate the cognitive educational activity of students in the classroom are indicated.

Keywords: Technology of problem-based learning, creative thinking, problem methods, problem situations, competence-based approach.

The technology of problem—based learning is the creation of problematic situations in educational activities and the organization of active independent activity of students to resolve them, as a result of which there is a creative mastery of knowledge, skills, mental abilities develop. [1]

The aim of the article is to reveal the content of the technology of problem-based learning in the conditions of the formation of educational and cognitive competencies of students.

Here are some research questions that guide this study as follows:

- What is problem-based learning based on?
- How are problematic situations created in the classroom?
- What are the disadvantages of this technology?

Problem-based learning is based on the creative positions of the American philosopher, psychologist and educator J. Dewey, who believed that the student repeats the path of humanity in his knowledge. He assimilates the material, not just by listening or perceiving with his senses, but as a result of satisfying his need for knowledge.[1]

To create problematic situations, the teacher leads students to a contradiction and suggests that they themselves find a way to resolve it [2]:

1. confronts contradictions in practice;
2. presents different points of view on the same question;
3. invites the class to consider the phenomenon from various positions (for example, from the point of view of a lawyer, financier, teacher);
4. encourages students to make comparisons, generalizations, conclusions from the situation, compare facts;
5. asks specific questions (for generalization, justification, specification, logic of reasoning);
6. defines problematic theoretical and practical tasks (for example, research);

7. suggests setting problematic tasks (for example, with insufficient or redundant initial data, with uncertainty in the formulation of the question, with contradictory data, with deliberately made mistakes, with limited decision times, to overcome "psychological inertia", etc.).

To implement the problematic technology, are necessary [1]:

1. selection of the most relevant, essential tasks;
2. defining the features of problem-based learning in various types of academic work;
3. building an optimal system of problem-based learning;
4. personal approach and skill of the teacher, capable of causing active cognitive activity of the student.

Since the indicator of the problematic nature of the lesson is the presence in its structure of the stages of search activity, it is natural that they represent the inner part in the structure of the problem lesson:

1. the emergence of a problem situation and the formulation of the problem;
2. making assumptions and substantiating the hypothesis;
3. proving the hypothesis; checking the correctness of the solution of the problem.

It also provides a more solid assimilation of knowledge (what is extracted independently is better absorbed and remembered for a long time); develops analytical thinking (conditions are analyzed, possible solutions are evaluated), logical thinking (requires proof of the correctness of the chosen solution, argumentation). [4]

But problem-based learning also has drawbacks. It is not always easy to formulate an educational problem, not all educational material can be constructed in the form of problems, problem-based learning does not contribute to the development of skills, it is not economical - it requires a lot of time.

Problem-based learning is designed to form a special style of mental activity, research activity and independence of students. The psychological basis of the

concept of problem-based learning is the theory of thinking as a productive process, proposed by S.L. Rubinstein. Thinking plays a leading role in the intellectual development of a person. Reflection itself is aimed at combining, conjugating, identifying the poles - opposites of the dialectical contradiction, thanks to which the latter is resolved.

Problem methods are methods based on the creation of problematic situations, active cognitive activity of students. Let's consider at the main characteristics of the general methods of problem-based learning that form students' competencies in practice.

How to teach students to resolve problematic situations in the classroom and apply the knowledge and skills they have gained in their own speech, including in a professionally oriented field?

26 university students took part in the study. The aim of this study was to teach students to develop creative and cognitive competencies for further use in professional activities using problem-based learning technology. We have made a step-by-step planning of several lessons to ensure a versatile impact on the intelligence of students through intensive speech and

mental activity. These lessons used forms that stimulated the desire of students to engage in communication in order to be understood. These include the use of structural and logical diagrams, pictures, tables, diagrams, as well as presentations. The formation of cognitive-cognitive competencies cannot be formed outside of activity.

Due to the use of various methods and forms focused on oral and written communication, this made it possible to have a versatile effect on the intelligence of students through intensive speech and mental activity. The lessons were compiled according to the book English file (Pre- Intermediate) by Christine Latham-Koenig Clive Oxenden. Fragments of the lessons are shown in Table 1.

When working on grammatical material, problem tasks are also used in order to activate the perception of new material and put students in the role of researchers.

For example, after explaining the method of tense formation, the present perfect tense, students are given the following task to independently identify the rules of its use: Table 2

Table 1

Analysis	Teacher	Students
Purpose: development of subject, meta-subject and personal UDS. 1. Setting a learning problem, generating ideas and building a plan to solve the problem Motivation. Creating a problem situation. The task at this stage into a communication situation and enter a problem situation based on an imagination task with the search for logical connections. <i>Technical means of training</i> <i>Task for the spread of opinions (in pairs)</i> <i>The urge to awareness to the problem</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We show a picture on the blackboard (to create a problem situation), then by means of a heuristic conversation, i.e. logically interrelated questions, we bring students to the problem question and certain conclusions. - The words on the slide will help you guess where we are going to travel today. - Where are we going? - Look at the illustrations, read the captions to them. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We work in pairs. The names of sights and cities are given on the sheet. Connect each landmark with the city where it is located with a line. - Where Carlton Gardens are located? - Was there one task? And how did you fulfill it? - Why did this happen? What don't we know yet? - So what topic will we go through? fixes the topic on the board 	Sydney, Melbourne, Perth, Canberra -We are going to Australia - In Meulbourne - And we think it's in Sydney. <i>experiencing surprise</i> - The task was one, but it was done in different ways! - We don't know the sights of Australia. - Australia

Read and compare:

Table 2

Past simple	Present Perfect tense
He played tennis yesterday. He read this book 3 weeks ago	He already has played tennis He has just read the book

Problematic presentation can be used in the study of tenses. Based on the name of the tense, students are invited to deduce the formula of education, as well as try to predict the cases of its use, which facilitates memorization and makes the process more interesting.

After analyzing the results of the reflection, during a practical experiment, we made the following findings:

1. The problem-based method of teaching activates the cognitive and educational activities of students in general, i.e. academic performance and the quality of knowledge significantly increases.

2. The use of problem-based learning technology in the classroom in combination with other forms of organization of educational activities of students is a prerequisite for modern classes at the university, because they provide the most complete and holistic assimilation of the material.

3. Problem-based learning is a purposeful educational activity aimed at achieving a specific goal according to a specific program for solving educational, research and practical tasks.

As a conclusion from the experience of using problem-based learning in English lessons, it can be noted that motivation to learn the language increases, students' activity and independence develop, and communication skills develop. This technology creates a favorable atmosphere in the classroom, relieves stress in students. As well as problem-based learning in a foreign language lesson has practical significance in the formation of personality.

Creating problematic situations in English lessons not only forms a system of knowledge, skills and abilities, which is provided by the program, but also develops students' creative activity in the most natural way. The situation of the student's difficulty in solving problems leads to the student's understanding of the insufficiency of his existing knowledge, which in turn causes

interest in knowledge and an attitude to acquire new ones. You should not be forced to blindly study the subject in pursuit of overall academic performance. It is necessary to give him the opportunity to experiment and not be afraid of mistakes, to educate students the courage to disagree with the teacher.

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